

Coordination polymers of copper(II) imides with polymeric heterocyclic Schiff bases of thiazole derivatives

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Two polymeric ligands, L₁ and L₂ were synthesized by polymerizing new heterocyclic Schiff bases 2-hydroxy-1-benzylidene-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole and 2-hydroxy-1-benzylidene-2-amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole, with 1,6-dichlorohexane. L₁, L₂ gave solid chelates with copper(II) phthalimide or succinimide. The metal ion is coordinated through nitrogen of imide ion, nitrogen of azomethine group and oxygen of deprotonated phenolic group of polyligands. The studies indicate square-planar ligand field around copper ion. The presence of coordinated water is proved in the polychelates.

Studies have been done on polychelates of polystyrene supported¹, salicylaldehyde-formaldehyde² and thiourea³ based polymers, but practically nothing is reported on the polymers of polymeric heterocyclic Schiff bases of thiazole derivatives. This communication describes the synthesis and characterization of some polymeric ligands derived from thiazoles and their polychelates with copper(II) imides.

Results and Discussion

The polychelates (Table 1) were found insoluble in most of the solvents, indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The chemical analysis data agree well with the 1 : 1 : 1 metal : ligand : water stoichiometry. These observations were confirmed by determination of average molecular weights by vapour pressure osmometry. This also indicates the presence of lower degree of polymerization and hence linear polymeric nature of the ligands in the polychelates. This can be substantiated on the basis of the fact that in the present polychelates, the *ortho*-position of the chain propagation site is already occupied by OH group and hence three-dimensional polymer can not result with 1,6-dichlorohexane⁴.

In the IR spectra, the presence of nitrogen coordinated imide molecule was proved by the shift of ν_{CO} from 1750 to 1700 cm^{-1} in the phthalimide polymers and from 1700 to 1670 cm^{-1} in the succinimide polymers⁵. The upward shift of ν_{CN} from 1480 to ≈ 1500 cm^{-1} supports this observation. The broad weak band at 2900 cm^{-1} due to hydrogen bonded phenolic OH of the polymeric ligands, disappeared in the spectra of the polymers, which indicates the deprotonation of the OH and its involvement in coordinations. The shift of $\nu_{\text{phenolic CO}}$ from 1300 to 1325 cm^{-1} also supports this opinion⁵. Two bands in the poly-ligands at 1580 (C=N) and 1620 cm^{-1} (ring C=N) shifted to 1610 and 1630 cm^{-1} respectively on chelation which confirms coordination through azomethine group⁷.

The room temperature magnetic moments of the polychelates (2.00–2.15 B.M.) are close to spin-only value⁸ due to two unpaired electrons. The reflectance spectra gave three bands at 34500, 15000 and 14000 cm^{-1} which are the usual bands of the square-planar copper(II) complexes⁹. The bands may, therefore, be assigned to charge transfer, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions¹⁰.

The complete thermal degradation took place in multiple steps but the first step of decomposition was taken as the criterion of thermal stability. The polyligands are stable upto $\sim 270^\circ$ while the polychelates upto $\sim 200^\circ$. After this range they start losing weight as was reflected in their TG and DTA curves. Thermal stability was found in the order : L₁ > L₂ > polychelate no. 1 > 2 > 3 > 4. The greater stability of the polymeric ligands than their polychelates suggests powerful intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the former¹¹. The decrease in the thermal stability of the polymeric ligands after coordination may also be attributed to the

Table 1. Physical data of the polymeric ligands and polychelates*

Polymeric ligands/ Polychelates ^a	Colour	M.p./ Decom. temp. °C	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
L ₁ (C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S)	Brown	280–290	—	—
L ₂ (C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₄ S)	Brown	275–290	—	—
[Cu(P)L ₁ (H ₂ O)] _n	Green	225–255	12.00 (11.88)	2.10
[Cu(P)L ₂ (H ₂ O)] _n	Green	215–240	9.50 (9.45)	2.15
[Cu(S)L ₁ (H ₂ O)] _n	Green	200–235	13.00 (13.05)	2.12
[Cu(S)L ₂ (H ₂ O)] _n	Green	220–260	10.50 (10.75)	2.14

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aPH = Phthalimide, C₈H₅O₂N; SH = succinimide, C₄H₅O₂N.

catalytic oxidation of the ligands by metal ion in the polymers¹². The thermograms of the polychelates reveal that there is a small increase in the weight at about 320°, which may be due to the formation of copper sulfate or copper sulfide¹³. The electrical conductivity of the polychelates was determined over the temperature range 50–250° in air. It was found to be in the range $(1.56-1.68) \times 10^{-8} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature, which increased regularly on increasing the temperature. The negative log of electrical conductivity of the polychelates was found to be linear function of reciprocal temperature. The values also reveal the role of *d*-electrons of copper ion in conduction. It is suggested⁴ that the metal is more effective when it forms square-planar complexes because the planar molecules are linked by metal *d*-orbital bonds perpendicular to the plane.

On the basis of all above informations a square-planar structure is proposed for the polychelates.

Experimental

1,2-Dichlorohexane (Sigma) was used. 2-Hydroxy-1-benzaldehyde (Sarabhai) distilled twice before use. Solvents (Glaxo/E. Merck) were distilled before use. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

All physical methods used were the same as reported earlier¹⁵.

Tetrahydrated copper(II) phthalimide or succinimide¹⁶ and Schiff bases and the polyligands¹⁶ were prepared as reported earlier.

The polymeric ligand (0.01 mol) was dissolved in DMF (25 ml) and to it an aqueous solution of the copper imide was added dropwise with constant stirring (30 min). A concentrated solution of ammonium acetate was then added with stirring. The mixture was refluxed over a water-bath at ~75° for 1 h. The resulting solid polychelates washed with DMF-alcohol-water mixture (1 : 1 : 1, v/v) and dried at room temperature.

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